

1 HES family transcription factors are activated during resistance to chemotherapy in TNBC cells.

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8 We observed HES family transcription factors activation during resistance to chemotherapy in TNBC cells.
9 Observed activation included, among other HES transcription factors, *HES6* and *HES7*.

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11 Citations

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